

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ELEMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STANDARD CURRICULUM FOR SPECIAL EDUCATION (KSSRPK) BY SPECIAL EDUCATION TEACHERS.

Rozaini Saharuddin (angahjhc@gmail.com)

Fakulti Pendidikan , Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia

Sapira Samat

Fakulti Pendidikan , Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia

Nadia Natrah Norhamdan

Fakulti Pendidikan , Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia

Mohd Hanafi Mohd Yasin

Fakulti Pendidikan , Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine special education teachers' attitudes and their knowledge towards the implementation of entrepreneurship in the Primary School Standard Curriculum (Kurikulum Standard Sekolah Rendah) or KSSR for special education. The survey was carried out in five primary schools integration in Miri, Sarawak and the sample comprised of 50 primary special education teachers (for learning disabilities classes). Besides, this study had identified the problems faced by special education teachers in implementing the entrepreneurship in KSSRPK. This study was conducted using a set of questionnaires and data were analyzed using SPSS version 22. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentages and mean. The result shows that, the total average mean score for knowledge on the implementation of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP) is 3.94 and the mean score for the attitude of special education teachers towards entrepreneurship is 3.86. This indicates the knowledge and attitudes of special education teachers are at a high and positive level. The findings also show that lack of times, no specific guidelines, no proper training and exposure on the elements itself and difficulties to accept new changes were among the problems faced by special education teachers during the implementation of the elements of entrepreneurship in their school.

Keywords: Implementation of Entrepreneurship, knowledge, attitude

Introduction

As with everything else, the field of education also experiences dynamic changes in today's globalised world which in turn demands similar changes in the curriculum. Beginning 2011, a curricular transformation known as Primary School Standard Curriculum (KSSR), emphasizing knowledge, skills and values which must be mastered by primary school students including students with learning disabilities, was introduced. The KSSR for Special Education for Learning Disabilities (KSSRPK (MP)) is based on the Primary School Integrated Curriculum (KBSR) and pivoted towards National Education Policy.

The incorporation of new elements in KSSRPK (MP) which includes entrepreneurship aims at instilling entrepreneurial culture in accordance with the current needs as well as future challenges. This new element must be applied in all primary school subjects (BPK 2013) in order to create a generation of envisioned entrepreneurs who have strong fundamentals in all aspects namely knowledge, thinking skills, social, creative, innovative and good ethics (BPK 2011).

In line with Vision 2020, the government focuses on generating a progressive Malaysian society, who is highly creative, highly resistant and highly skilled. Therefore entrepreneurial skill is an important soft skill to be mastered by students including those who have learning disabilities (Norasmah 2003 & Rosli 2008)

Special education teachers (MP) act as the catalyst and generators of human capital integrating entrepreneurship in education in their teachings. This entrepreneurial skill should also be instilled in special needs students who have constitutional rights to have the same education with their typical peers (KPM 2001). For that to be achieved, the teachers are instrumental in making this educational transformation a success. Hence, the teachers face insurmountable challenges. Teachers who lack the much needed skills will adversely affect efforts by the government. Teachers must master the entrepreneurial skill for a successful teaching process, inside as well as outside the classroom. They are recommended to continuously upgrade and improve their abilities and skills and should be highly innovative and creative (Hanum, 2008) to keep up with the times.

However, the study conducted by the Curricular Development Division (2011) discovered that the main problem with Primary School Integrated Curriculum (KBSR) and Secondary School Integrated Curriculum (KBSM) was that entrepreneurial development in students was performed in an indirect manner even though entrepreneurial teaching was already incorporated since early 1990s. This finding was also supported by Nor Aishah (2013) who found entrepreneurial education was not given the proper emphasis in the primary school curriculum as there were still many reports, discussions and studies being conducted on the methods used to teach entrepreneurship in classroom.

Therefore, this study is conducted to gauge the knowledge and attitude of special education teachers in relation to entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP). It also aims at identifying the problems and issues faced by these teachers in applying entrepreneurship in their teachings.

Adaptive Control of Thought Theory
The theory of adaptive control of thought, introduced by Anderson (1983), proposes that

thoughts create actions. These thoughts occurred due to the interactions between knowledge about a fact, followed by attitudes. This theory can be related to teacher's entrepreneurial knowledge which will generate positive attitudes in the teachers in applying entrepreneurial element in their teaching process which in turn will further motivate and encourage students to learn and master basic entrepreneurial skills.

Figure 1 - Research Design

Research Methodology

This quantitative research survey utilises questionnaires as the instrument to gauge teachers' knowledge and attitude on the application of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP). The questionnaire is divided into four parts. Part A is about respondent's background. There are five items on Part B which measures teacher's knowledge on the application of entrepreneurship meanwhile there are four items on Part C which measures teacher's attitude towards the application of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP). There are seven items on Part D on the problems faced by teachers in applying entrepreneurship in their teachings. The research sample consists of 50 special education teachers at an integrated primary school in Miri, Sarawak.

Research Findings

Respondents' Demographic Information

The accumulated data was analysed using descriptive analysis via the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 For Windows in order to obtain the frequencies, percentages and the mean value. The research findings are based on the sequence of the questionnaire. Part A of the questionnaire captures the demographic information of respondents in terms of gender, educational qualifications and experience. The data is shown in the Table 1

Table 1 - Respondent's Demography

Information	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	14 respondents	28 %
Female	36 respondents	72 %
Education Qualification		
Diploma in Education	26 respondents	52 %
Bachelor in Education	17 respondents	34 %
Teaching Certificate	7 respondents	14 %
Teaching Experience		
1 – 5 years	22 respondents	44 %
6 – 10 years	20 respondents	40 %
11 years and above	8 respondents	16 %

These findings were accumulated from 50 respondents, 14 males (20%) and 36 females (80%) who are special education teachers in the district of Miri. The research show that the majority of the respondents are teachers with a diploma in education consisting of 16 teachers (75%), 4 respondents (20%) have a bachelor degree in education and 1 respondent (5%) is holding a teaching certificate. The majority of the respondents have 6-10 years teaching experience which is 11 of them (55%), 7 respondents (35%) have a 1 to 5 years' experience and only 2 respondents have more than 11 years of experience teaching special education.

Knowledge of Special Education Teachers Applying Entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP)

The following is the analysis on Part B which measures the teachers' knowledge on the application of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP). The items were tested in order to obtain the means and standard deviation. The findings are as shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2 - Teachers Knowledge To Apply Entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP)

Item	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interp.
1.	Entrepreneurship is an individual who practices how an entrepreneur thinks and acts.	3.96	0.53	High
2.	Entrepreneurial characteristics can be created through the application of entrepreneurship in teaching and learning (PDP).	4.04	0.49	High

3.	There are five main elements applied as an exposure to entrepreneurial attitude.	3.94	0.5 1	High
4.	Giving exposure to students with learning disabilities solve problems and	3.92	0.5 3	High
5.	empower them to make life decisions. The application of entrepreneurship are in the Basic Core Module and Thematic Core Module.	3.84	0.6 2	High
Average Mean		3.94		High

The average mean value of teacher's knowledge to apply entrepreneurship is 3.94 indicating that the special education teachers in the Miri district have good knowledge on the application of entrepreneurship in their teachings. The highest mean is the creation of entrepreneurial characteristics through the implementation of entrepreneurship in education. The skills mastered by students through the application of entrepreneurship in the teaching and learning process are able to develop students' knowledge and skills as well as having a positive influence in creating entrepreneurial attitudes. Entrepreneurial knowledge and experience possess by the teachers can give the much needed exposure to the students where the teachers will be able to use the knowledge and experience gained to teach students.

Bernstein and Carayannis (2011) found that the higher the students' knowledge in entrepreneurship the bigger is their interest in entrepreneurial education. This finding is also supported by the study conducted by Syed Zambri (2013) who stated that the entrepreneurial education taught to primary students in order for them to be high quality individuals who can contribute to the development of human capital where they can use the knowledge that they have gained in their everyday life as well as help them to venture new skills and technology.

The Attitude of Special Education Teachers On the Application of Entrepreneurship In KSSRPK (MP)

Table 3 below demonstrates the attitude of teachers in the application of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP)

Table 3 - Attitude Of Teachers On The Application of Entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP)

Item	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interp.
1.	I like to encourage students with learning disabilities to	4.04	0.60	High

	have interest in entrepreneurship.			
2.	I like to apply entrepreneurship in order for the students to love learning.	4.12	0.69	High
3.	I am not skilful in using various PDP strategies in applying entrepreneurship.	3.24	0.87	Average
4.	I believe that by applying entrepreneurship,my students with learning disabilities will be prepared for a career.	4.04	0.75	High
Average Mean		3.89		

Table 3 demonstrates the attitude of teachers on the application of entrepreneurship in KSSRPK (MP). On average the respondents portray positive attitude on the application of entrepreneurship in the curriculum. The highest mean is teachers prefer to incorporate entrepreneurial element in PDP to encourage the students to love studying. Teachers who adopt a positive attitude will use their creativity to make the learning environment more conducive for the students. Teachers must opt for a teaching method which is in accordance with the students' abilities. The methods used to enliven learning including demonstration, simulation, games, co-teaching, role playing and project based method. These approaches provide real life experience to the students where they will be placed in real life situations and given the opportunity to make decisions (Nor Aishah 2013).

It will also encourage students to be actively involved and to think of finding their own solutions and this makes for a smoother and more fun teaching and learning.

Issues Faced by Special Education Teachers In Applying Entrepreneurship IN KSSRPK (MP)

The issues faced by teachers in applying entrepreneurship in KSSRPK(MP) are shown in Table4:

Table 4 - Problems In The Application Of TMK

Item	Statement	Scale	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Teaching aids are enough.	Highly disagree		
		Disagree	6	12%
		Somewhat disagree	15	30%
		Agree	26	52%
		Highly agree	3	6%
2.	Not enough time to apply	Highly disagree	2	4%

	creativity and innovations in teaching.	Disagree	17	34%
		Somewhat disagree	24	48%
		disagree	5	10%
		Agree	2	4%
		Highly agree		
3.	No specific guidance in implementing creativity and innovations in KSSRPK (MP).	Highly disagree	2	4%
		Disagree	19	38%
		Somewhat disagree	22	44%
		disagree	5	10%
		Agree	2	4%
		Highly agree		
4.	No induction course on how to apply creativity and innovation in school.	Highly disagree	17	34%
		Disagree	23	46%
		Somewhat disagree	9	18%
		disagree	1	2%
		Agree		
		Highly agree		
5.	Administrators provide support to apply creativity and innovations in learning disabilities' curriculum.	Highly disagree	2	4%
		Disagree	12	24%
		Somewhat disagree	30	60%
		disagree	6	12%
		Agree		
6.	No follow up course to increase teachers' knowledge in applying creativity and innovations in KSSRPK(MP).	Highly agree	10	20%
		Highly disagree	23	46%
		Disagree	12	24%
		Somewhat disagree	3	6%
		disagree	2	4%
		Agree		
		Highly agree		
7.	Teachers who cannot accept new changes in their teachings.	Highly disagree	3	6%
		Disagree	15	30%
		Somewhat disagree	20	40%
		disagree	10	20%
		Agree	2	4%
		Highly agree		

In general, the problems faced by special education teachers are mild. The findings show that the main issue faced by the teachers in implementing value added element is the exposure that they need in terms of courses on the approaches and methods to be used. Through courses, trainings, workshops and discussions on the methods to incorporate

elements in teaching and learning will generate more and consistent ideas to be used in the classrooms. This also ensures teachers to be more prepared and are more passionate to organise various activities and adopt more techniques in teaching and learning. The findings of this research are in line with that conducted by Norfadhilah (2014) and Nor Izah(2011) which state that trainings and workshops can improve teachers' knowledge and skills. The knowledge and skills in applying value added elements in the classroom should be enforced and improved from time to time by providing more opportunities for special education teachers to follow the latest and comprehensive trainings to enable the teachers to incorporate creativity, innovation, entrepreneurship, information technology and communication in the classroom effectively and continuously.

Discussion and Recommendations

The application of entrepreneurship in classroom teaching is vital especially for students with learning disabilities. Teachers play a crucial role in instilling entrepreneurial readiness in these students. This implementation encourages creativity and innovations, problem solving, high sustainability, adoption of skills and can develop individual competencies.

In addition, entrepreneurship can pique the students' interests, making learning fun and the students more active and creative. Having said that, teachers should also adopt various PDP methods in teaching entrepreneurship to ensure learning objectives can be achieved. The research findings clearly show that good knowledge and teachers' positive attitude in the teaching of entrepreneurship can encourage students to learn the basic skills. The findings are in line with that found by Rosnaini (2006) which states that good knowledge of teachers create positive attitudes. It is recommended for teachers to follow periodical trainings on the teaching of entrepreneurship in PDP to ensure teachers receive seamless information. This will definitely make the teachers' PDP more effective.

Conclusion

The research clearly states that teachers should have good knowledge especially about entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is a new development that has presence in almost every aspect of societal life and learning. Teachers with high knowledge will adopt more positive attitude on the implementation of entrepreneurship in their teachings to affect active learning among the students, encourages interactions and cooperation as well as to encourage immediate response. However, entrepreneurship application in the PDP needs proper planning. Therefore, special education teachers must strive to increase their knowledge and adopt positive attitude in implementing entrepreneurship in their teaching to make it a success.

References

- Azhar Muhammad, Siti Maisarah Bahrin. (2010). *Persediaan Guru Pelatih Pendidikan Islam Universiti Teknologi Malaysia UTM Bagi memenuhi Modal Insan*, Skudai, Johor.
- Abdullah Mat Rashid & Gene W. Gloeckner. (2006). Information & Learning Technology (ILT) Adoption Among Career & Technical Teacher in Malaysia. The electronic journal on Information Systems in developing Countries.
- Alina Margaritoiu (2010). Teachers Perception's Concerning Computer Use. International Conference Education & Educational Psychology.
Bahagian Pembangunan Kurikulum. Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia. 2013. Putrajaya.
- Bernstein, A. & Carayannis, E. 2011. How do resource bundles develop and change in new ventures? A dynamic model and longitudinal exploration. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* 25(3): 37-58
- Hanum Hassan, Razli Ahmad dan Lt. Kol. (B) Azuddin Bahari. 2008. *Kemahiran Insaniah dan Kepentingan Penerapannya dalam Program Bakti Siswa Perdana Unimap*. Pusat Kemahiran Komunikasi Unimap.
- Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia. 2006. *Pelan Induk Pembangunan Pendidikan 2006-2010*. Putrajaya. Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia.
- Kementerian Pelajaran Malaysia. (2011). *Kurikulum Standard Sekolah Rendah Pendidikan Khas Masalah Pembelajaran*. Putrajaya
- Norasmah Hj. Othman, Zaidatul Akmaliah Lope Pihie, Mohd Ibrahim Nazri & Rohani Ahmad Tarmizi. 2003. Aplikasi Model Kolb dalam Program Keusahawanan Remaja *Jurnal Teknologi*, 38(E). UTM
- Nor Aishah Buang. 2013. *Pendidikan Keusahawanan*. UKM
- Rosli Mahmood, Azrain Nasyrah Mustapa, Rosli Mohd Saad, Mohamad Yusof Mohd jani, Norria Zakaria, Syahrina Abdullah, Ahmad Khairi Yahya, Hoe Chee Hee, Shamsul Huda Abd Rani, Muhammaa Shukri Bakar, Shiza Sa'atar, Lily Julienty Abu Bakar, Habshah bakar. 2010. *Prinsip-prinsip keusahawanan: Pendekatan gunaan Edisi 2*. Cengage Learning Asia Pte. Ltd. Singapore.
- Syed Zamberi Ahmad. 2013. The Need for Inclusion of Entrepreneurship education in Malaysia Lower and Higher Learning institution. *Emerald*: 191-203